

Virtual Vaka: A Computational Tool for Thinking About Seafaring

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Abstract

Seafaring has had a profound impact on human history and is a fundamental component of many narratives of the deep past. While ancillary signals of seafaring are widespread in the archaeological record, direct evidence for ancient seafaring technology and knowledge is scarce, leaving a great deal of uncertainty about past maritime activity. This uncertainty lends itself to a model-based approach, which is manifest in a long history of computer simulation particularly in the Pacific. Changes in data availability, computing technology, and modelling philosophies have shifted the role of computational modelling in the historical sciences (Bevan 2015), encouraging a diversity of approaches to address a wider range of questions at an increasing scale and complexity. Here, we discuss our efforts to develop computational models of seafaring in the past as “tools to think with”: technologies that can be deployed in the iterative process of theory-building. The latest version of our agent-based simulation, Virtual Vaka, can send vessels out with a variety of navigational and technological capabilities across the globe. The model draws on environmental data obtained from a range of open sources, allowing for exploration of voyages using real weather conditions from the last 70 years, while also maintaining the capacity to use modelled data for both weather and bathymetry to simulate past journeys as far back as the Pleistocene. These and other design choices enable a diversity of cases to be explored and experiments to be customised, opening channels for engagement with a wider range of knowledge-holders. We re-examine case studies used in Davies and Bickler (2015) with the latest version of the software demonstrating how new improvements add to the understanding of both historic seafaring and climate change studies.

Keywords: Seafaring; Agent Based Modelling; Pacific Settlement; Climate Change

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1. Introduction

Seafaring has had a profound impact on human history and is a fundamental component of many narratives of the deep past. While ancillary signals of seafaring are widespread in the archaeological record, direct evidence for ancient seafaring technology and knowledge is scarce, leaving a great deal of uncertainty about past maritime activity. This uncertainty lends itself to a model-based approach, which is manifest in a long history of computer simulation particularly in the Pacific (e.g., Callaghan 2003a, 2003b; Callaghan and Fitzpatrick 2008; Fitzpatrick 2025; Di Piazza et al. 2007; Doussett and Di Piazza 2021; Fitzpatrick and Callaghan 2013; Irwin et al. 1990; Levinson et al. 1973; Montenegro et al. 2016; Perttola 2022). Changes in data availability, computing technology, and modelling philosophies have shifted the role of computational modelling in the historical sciences (Bevan 2015), encouraging a diversity of approaches to address a wider range of questions at an increasing scale and complexity (Verhagen 2018).

Here, we discuss our efforts to develop computational models of seafaring in the past as “tools to think with” (Davies 2018; Davies and Bickler 2015): technologies that can be deployed in the iterative process of theory-building. The latest version of our agent-based simulation, Virtual Vaka, can send vessels out with a variety of navigational and technological capabilities across the globe. The model draws on environmental data obtained from a range of open sources, allowing for exploration of voyages using real weather conditions from the last 70 years, while also maintaining the capacity to use modelled data for both weather and bathymetry to simulate past journeys as far back as the Pleistocene. These and other design choices enable a diversity of cases to be explored and experiments to be customised, opening channels for engagement with a wider range of knowledge-holders. We re-examine case studies used in Davies and Bickler (2015) with the latest version of the software and demonstrate how the new improvements add to the understanding of both historic seafaring and climate change studies.

2. Modelling Seafaring in the Pacific

The principal reason we model past seafaring is the contrast between the importance of seafaring in human history and the limited amount of data that exists to inform on those processes in the deep past. While there have been noteworthy findings of watercraft, rigging, and depictions in archaeological contexts (summarized by Anderson 2022, 2024a, 2024b; Irwin et al. 2019, 2022 recently for the Pacific), these are only a small number of data points in what was probably a wider variety of adaptations to travel over water, leaving many questions about past voyages of exploration and interaction. Modelling of past seafaring, particularly with computer software, has been one of the few ways these uncertainties have been interrogated systematically. Elements that we understand well, such as sea levels or viewsheds, can be combined with elements we do not, such as vessel performance (Anderson 2017; Irwin et al. 2022) or course awareness, in such a way as to explore the potential outcomes from a range of possible histories.

As Gal et al. (2021) have recently emphasized, seafaring involved not just the knowledge associated with the building of vessels but an embedded knowledge of the local and regional environment. Choosing when and if to sail could be just as critical as the ability to sail. Indeed, Garcia

et al.'s (2001) analysis of the Manila galleons crossing of the northern Pacific demonstrates how quickly Spanish sailors incorporated hemisphere-scale weather and geography information into systematic trade from the 15th century AD onwards. This likely involved picking up the better times of the years to sail, the routes to take, and strategies to reduce risk and mitigate disaster.

There is a long history of inquiry into Pacific seafaring and our interest is focused principally on this region. This includes experimental studies such as the adventures of Thor Heyerdahl in *Kon Tiki* in the 1940s (Heyerdahl 1968) and the use of Indigenous methods since the 1970s by the Polynesian Voyaging Society and *Hokule'a* (Finney 1994). There is also a parallel history of computational models, including the drift simulations of Levinson et al. (1973) in the 1970s, directed sailing simulations of Irwin et al. (1990; Irwin 1992) in the 1990s, and the shortest path models of Montenegro and colleagues (2008, 2016) more recently. While these examples are unique to the Pacific, the ongoing interplay between experimentation and modelling is a quality shared with other regions as well (see Slayton 2018: 53ff for a review).

Flash forward to 2024, and the study of seafaring in the past has grown remarkably. There is increased dialogue across multiple regions and new approaches, particularly those using GIS least cost path and network-based methods, are seeing expanded applications. This work is generating new hypotheses regarding seafaring, human expansions, and interactions in the past (e.g., Montenegro 2024, Slayton 2018: 243).

3. Experiments with Virtual Vaka

This model is coded in R (R Core Team 2023), while the user interface is programmed using the Shiny package (Chang et al. 2023). This approach uses open-source software and data, making it easy to access for a wide number of users. The web-based graphical interface allows interested users to experiment with the parameters to improve interactivity and engagement (Figure 1). The same code can be run using a set of experiment parameters that can be saved, modified, and reused. These experiments can be used with larger numbers of voyages and across the timespan of the underlying data for subsequent statistical analysis and graphical plots. The code leverages parallel processing and can be scaled up to run hundreds of thousands of voyages.

The model uses freely available historical data for winds and currents, imported as NetCDF files (a format to stack time-based geographic data), and geographic information. Data are cycled through sequentially, based on user-defined dates in defined increments (e.g., hourly, 6 hourly, daily). Dates can be preset in experiments to explore different kinds of conditions, for example, variation in equatorial currents. Our default data sets include:

1. Gridded winds (2.5° resolution) from the NCEP-NCAR Reanalysis 1 dataset, which includes global daily wind reconstructions from 1948 through to near present day allowing us over 70 years of sailing time (Kalany et al. 1996).
2. Gridded ocean surface currents data from the Ocean Surface Current Analyses Real-time (OSCAR) 1/3° resolution data collected in a 5-day cycle from 1993 to 2021 (Bonjean and Lagerloef 2002).

- Vector land boundaries are based on the Natural Earth 10m physical vector dataset (naturalearthdata.com) with several modifications to add some small islands and rocks in the areas we study in more detail.

The simulation code can be adapted to use alternative data sources as well, including modeled climate and ocean data, both more detailed regional datasets and with finer resolution. This is important as although “real” data is being used they are an approximation of real conditions which involve interactions between the winds, currents and vessels that are not captured at the resolution of actual sailing (see discussion Avis et al. 2007:200-201). Vessel information is derived from published data sources related to leeward drift profiles and wind performance. This can be modified to compare how different performance characteristics affect outcomes.

Figure 1: Main view of the online version of Virtual Vaka

3.1. Modeling Sailing Ability

The capabilities of seafarers in the past varied significantly across time, with less sophisticated approaches during the Pleistocene giving rise to the deep ocean crossings developed by many populations in different places during the Holocene (e.g., Callaghan 2003a, b, 2015, Hölzchen, et al. 2022, Montenegro 2024, Smith 2020, Slayton et al. 2022; see further references below). Our approach to the question of human decision-making and navigation is to imagine a spectrum between a person helplessly adrift at sea on a raft through to one who is completely aware of their location and fully able to exploit their vessel’s capabilities. Early simulations in the Pacific (Levison et al. 1973; Wild 1985) focused on drift and paddling were dominated by environmental factors and measures of the relative cost of different corridors for travel that resulted. Modeled sailing capacities were constrained by preset approaches to manage wind patterns or focused on a small set of

simplified course selections. These were not always reflective of some of the likely responses that sailors would have been capable of making, especially in more difficult conditions.

3.2. *Drift and Paddle*

Several simulations have examined the use of “drift” voyaging (e.g., Callaghan 2015; Fitzpatrick 2013; Levinson et al. 1973). Drifting has been well described and involves two major processes. Firstly, sea currents are the usually the primary influence on the paths taken by floating objects. Secondly, objects on the water are also subject to varying amounts of wind force depending on their profile. This “leeward” component varies by size and shape of vessel as well as its ability to be steered. The combination of the current force and direction, and the effect of the wind on the moving vessel can be calculated. In this simulation, as with most others, it is done using the leeward drift profile and performance as described by the US Coast Guard (2013: 440-443) which provides a range of performance figures for people floating through to large vessels. In Virtual Vaka, the parameters that relate to specific models of vessels described by the USCG (2013), such as kayaks or rafts, can be chosen and adjusted as well to provide further fine tuning of the leeward drift “performance”.

Paddling is an additional element within drift models which can modify the influences of the current and leeward drift by direction and speed (Horvath and Finney 1976; Slayton 2018). At the same time, paddling brings human physiological limits into consideration, which would constrain the duration of time it can be maintained, and any times spent without paddling would revert to drift controls. In many cases, paddling in the deep ocean in contrary conditions would have been impractical, especially on vessels that would have been small enough to manoeuvre while still having sufficient supplies to survive for long periods (c.f. Anderson 2022).

Figure 2 shows a sample of drift voyages from San Ana Island in the Solomons using Virtual Vaka. The kayak-type craft head off in mid-August using data from 1994-1999 where conditions are good for heading to the east for 15-20 days. When things go well, they can get to Nendō Island in the Santa Cruz Islands reasonably successfully (67%).

Figure 3 shows the endpoints of 15 days drifting without paddling with kayaks sent every day for 20 years based on data from 1993-2012. Unsurprisingly, seasonal patterns become quite apparent with Southern Hemisphere summer months pushing craft to the west and winter months more easterly. However, survival is becomes unlikely, with rates of finding landing somewhere around 50% and the majority of that being vessels just making it to the large neighboring island of San Cristobal. Success is very seasonal and based on ideal conditions to make progress in the desired direction. Survivability is one measure, but logs of the simulated voyages can be used to calculate other indicators like the frequency and intensity of countervailing conditions and the lengths of successful voyages to provide other comparative insights.

Figure 4 shows a similar set of parameters to the first results, however, we introduce the process of running the simulations backwards. Here the destination of a voyage is determined but the simulation is run to compare the likelihood of different origin points given assumptions about how a vessel and its navigator would fare under prevailing conditions. As differences based on initial conditions are critical when undertaking drift voyaging and paddling against strong ocean conditions, this makes analysis of evaluating likely corridors or pathways between places more overt.

When temporal sequences of environmental data are used and navigational decision-making follow fixed routines, the results are the same whether simulations in Virtual Vaka are run forward or backward. However, the difference between forward and backward modeling becomes significant

when using stochastically modeled past environmental data (e.g., Callaghan 2003b, 2015, Irwin et al. 1990, Montenegro et al. 2014, 2016) and voyaging strategies where small changes can result in voyages with very different trajectories. Therefore, the modelling results can be used as a measure of the sensitivity or robustness of the links between origins and destinations. Running simulations in this way provides some ways around the limitations of the deterministic, network and least-cost paths approaches (e.g., Montenegro et al. 2016, Pertolla 2022, Rorabaugh 2025) which can obfuscate the importance of contingency: the easier path is not always the path taken. Each approach has different uses for understanding voyaging in the past.

Figure 2. Drift voyages from San Cristobal in mid-August (20 days, 1994-1999, top) with bottom figure showing a simulation output of one example in more detail with relation to leeward effects (blue arrows) and current (red arrows) acting at points along the route. Island targets in green showing 0.2° (~22km around the equator) buffer.

Figure 3: End points of drift voyages from Santa Ana (X) (Solomon Islands) from 1993-2012 (top); Success rates of drift voyages from Santa Ana by year (left) and by month (right)

Figure 4: Reverse drift voyages back to San Cristobal from Nendō in mid-August (1994-1999, top) with green areas showing expanded buffer zones for targets

3.3. Course Management, Positional Awareness and Windward Progress

An area of research that remains underexplored in simulated seafaring is the incorporation of navigational knowledge. Typical for navigated voyages, previous models (e.g., Irwin 1992; Irwin et al. 1990) usually give the navigator the ability to hold a specific course. Vessels are given a starting point and then select a direction to be sailed and are sent off in that direction. Less simple strategies may then include changes to that chosen course based on time at sea or some measure of positional awareness such as a specific latitude and/or an estimated position (see e.g., Irwin 1992; Irwin et al. 1990). In *Virtual Vaka*, an uncertainty can be incorporated into desired direction to create some “fuzziness” in the voyages.

When the wind direction is against the desired course, sailors must tack. Tacking is the means of making progress against the wind by sailing between two points close to it and requires both technological capacity and navigational know-how. In the Pacific, the ability of vessels to tack is a fundamental assumption underlying many traditional models (e.g., Irwin 1992), and one that has been questioned based on ethnohistoric data regarding sails used in Remote East Polynesia (Anderson 2017; Goodwin et al. 2014). In cases where the ability to tack is more firmly established, it may be reasonable to simplify this in terms of, and adjustment to, speed. However, choices regarding optimal tacking and duration might fundamentally alter a course path.

These are influenced by the construction options of the vessels themselves. These range from simple rafts, through to large ships used for all manner of seafaring including exploration, whaling, trade and colonization. Modelling the dynamics of these vessels lies at a confluence of archaeological

and historical research, engineering modelling and detailed sailing knowledge of groups around the world (e.g., Evans 2008; Irwin et al. 2022; United States Coast Guard 2013, for related examples).

In Virtual Vaka, the close-hauled tacking angle is determined by the no-go-zone in a polar diagram (Kimball 2009). If the desired course is against the wind, the virtual navigators can be set up to choose tacks on either side of a headwind randomly, or optimally based on desired course made good, and with an associated degree of uncertainty. Optimizing a tack means directing the boat to sail as close to the desired course while still ensuring that speed is maintained for progress (Gal et al. 2021; Palmer 2009). As a result, both the uncertainties in course-setting and the vessels' ability to tack are key indicators of navigational capability and are modelled in the simulation. A navigator who is aware of their latitude and that of their target might make different decisions before and during a voyage than a navigator trying to sail a course without that knowledge. There are numerous techniques a navigator could use to identify their position at sea. Dead reckoning, use of stars and seamarks, maps, magnetic compasses, time pieces, or satellite positioning equipment can provide increasingly more precise estimates of where a vessel is on the ocean surface. For the simulation, we also wanted to be able to model voyages where the navigators could estimate their position at sea with different degrees of accuracy and then make required adjustments to reach a specific goal.

An example of a method we employ in the simulation is inspired by the Micronesian *etak* system (Gunn 1980), which uses the position of a series of stars on the horizon relative to an island to establish relative distance and direction to that island or another. Using this method, virtual navigators exploring an unknown area set a notional target based on expected travel over several days and then used a series of stars relative to that target to establish their distance between start and target. This information can also be used to constrain tack lengths in adverse winds so as not to miss a target as the vessel draws nearer. The model is not using stars movements themselves but exploring the possible navigational aims and outcomes that may have been achievable.

Implementing a celestial navigation system within a simulation could be accomplished in several ways that vary in terms of complexity and complication; for our purposes, using a target to adjust the course heading balanced our desire include a navigational aid based on known or perceived locations with model simplicity and computational expediency. In its simplest form, a target location is chosen, and the desired heading of the vessel is adjusted towards that target on an hourly or daily basis. This makes little difference in the initial stages of a voyage unless the vessel is sent off in the wrong direction! However, as the vessel gets closer to the target, it will make greater course corrections if it has been unable to make sufficient progress.

Given sufficient time, the vessel is therefore likely to arrive at its target, at which point either it will stop, it can be made to move onto a second target or return home. The model can use any location as a target, not necessarily an island or landmass, as well as any position along the axis running from the original desired direction outwards to that target. The use of these navigational targets can be used to under- or over-shoot a specific island objective and in some situations allow the simulated voyage more closely mimics a specific compass or star-navigated voyage. This usefulness of this remains does still require more refinement.

3.4. *Aotearoa Back to the Tropics*

To see how this works, Figure 5 shows four voyages leaving Cape Reinga in far northern New Zealand in the direction of Rarotonga in the southern Cook Islands. Here, the objective is not to

reconstruct a specific voyage, instead, we want to explore what kinds of techniques might facilitate a successful voyage. The voyages all leave in late June 1994 with varying abilities to sail into the wind. Their ability to hold the desired course is limited by a headwind no-go zone varying between 75°, 90° and 105° into either side of the wind. In the voyages, the vessels find initially favorable winds up to about 27° south and stay with their desired course, bypassing the Kermadec Islands on the way. After this, winds turn against the bow, and the vessel begins to tack.

Figure 5: Voyages from Cape Reinga towards Rarotonga showing different tracks based on size of the no-go zone for sailing into the wind (75-105) requiring tacking and use of positional awareness feature to reset tacking choices based on target of Rarotonga (Dashed line)

All three voyages with no target positional awareness consistently pass to the west of Rarotonga as they try to maintain a heading in adverse winds. Vessels with better windward capabilities get nearer to Rarotonga but their original heading takes them further north. One vessel does find Niue and survives while the others run out of time in empty ocean. However, the vessel using target positional capability can tack back and forth as it passes the latitude of its target and makes successful landfall (Figure 5). This demonstrates how the simulation allows for testing of the balance between vessel performance and navigator abilities to achieve specific outcomes.

There are myriad different parameter settings to be explored, and this approach gives the virtual navigator particular capabilities before and during the voyage and lets a path or corridor (sensu Slayton 2018) emerge. This can be varied by systematically removing these capacities or adding others. In this way, we can explore what kinds of knowledge may be necessary to make specific voyages, or how voyaging success improves with innovation. One conclusion is that while tacking capability is important for sailing, the ability to determine, hold and then adjust headings towards a notional target may be a more crucial factor in determining whether vessels are able to sail in difficult wind patterns. Virtual Vaka now includes an animated surface viewer chart to allow examination of how simulated voyages react to daily changes in wind and/or currents encountered (Figure 6). This allows users to visualize navigator responses during a voyage and also identify the wind and current patterns that lead to different outcomes.

This becomes more complex in the situation around Aotearoa New Zealand if we examine debates around vessel capabilities and the implications for settlement. Anderson (2017, 2022, 2024a, 2024b; Godwin et al. 2014) argues that archaeologists have overestimated some of the technological options available to Pacific sailors and especially the types of sails available and resulting ability to make progress against the wind (Gal et al. 2021; Palmer 2008). This has resulted in a far more limited capability upwind, “windward passages with rigs such as the double spritsail required understanding and use of periodic wind reversal plus ancillary propulsion by paddle (Anderson 2024a: Footnote 92). It was seafaring skill that counted more than advanced sailing technology” (Anderson 2022: 64, 2024b).

This is in part a rebuttal of Irwin (1992) and simulation there (see also Irwin et al. 1990) for Polynesian settlement and more recent work relating to vessel hull shapes. Irwin et al. (2022: 42) conclude that changes in hull shape reduced hydrodynamic lift required for windward sailing, and that sailing capability had been in “more general decline ... with a shift from multi-hulls to monohulls, a loss of roll stability, more paddling and downwind sailing”. The difficulty with portrayal of the changes in terms of an evolutionary decline, is that it undervalues the changes that Anderson (2022, 2023) identifies relating to sail types and paddling that reflect a shift from long-distance voyages of exploration to near-shore and inter-island travel within island groups.

It is beyond of the scope of this paper to resolve these contrasting perspectives of the sailing around Aotearoa New Zealand in pre-colonial times. However, the advantages of simulation studies are that they do allow the testing of the consequences of different technological adaptations as it is not always known which elements were critical to achieve the outcomes historically observed (cf Anderson 2017: 2ff). The challenge for the simulations is to ensure that they are sufficiently sophisticated to capture those technological and environmental factors to distinguish outcomes that had, could have or could not have occurred. One outcome of this debate is that Virtual Vaka now can combine paddling, sailing and drift capabilities in different configurations to explore how ancillary

strategies can assist voyages between known locations in different conditions. Future simulation experiments will be required to explore the outcomes of these configurations.

Yellow arrow shows desired course and blue arrow shows wind direction at canoe position

Figure 6: Snapshot of animated surface viewer in Virtual Vaka showing winds (top) and currents (bottom) with canoe moving along the resulting path (black line)

4. Seafaring for Climate Studies

To illustrate some of the capabilities of the simulation we return to one of our favorite case studies. This comes from Garcia et al. (2001), who studied galleon logs to evaluate changes in the length of crossings from Mexico and the Philippines between the 16th and 18th centuries. Using assessments of sailing efficiency for galleons, and the same NCEP wind data we use in our study, Garcia et al. (2001) argued that systematic increases in voyage durations could be associated with changes in atmospheric circulation in the Pacific.

During our previous work on simulations in the northern Pacific (Davies and Bickler 2015) we were able to produce similar results to those of Garcia et al. (2001). They had suggested that initial westward crossing of the Pacific under winds from El Niño conditions as part of El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) added approximately an extra week to the voyages to the Philippines over those during non-ENSO. They attributed this to weather systems appearing east of the Philippines towards the end of the voyages which made progress to the Philippines difficult. The galleons in theirs, and our simulations, set out from Acapulco, Mexico on a bearing of 210° until they reach the 13th Parallel North. From there they sail along that latitude across the Pacific until they reach the Mariana Islands, tacking up to 60° off the wind when necessary. At the Marianas, the positional awareness option was then used to navigate the galleons on a course to Embocadero de San Bernardino on the western edge of the Philippines (Garcia et al. 2001). This is different to simply setting a direction, as the galleons can correct their course daily to get to the specific target, rather than take a set direction. If they encountered parts of the Philippines prior to hitting the target the voyages stopped, but they were still considered to have “succeeded” as they would have simply shifted around the coastline to the exact location in a relatively short time.

The performance of the galleons was based on Garcia et al.’s (2001: 2453) assessment of performance into the wind and reaching a maximum speed of around 13 knots downwind. In Virtual Vaka, galleons were sent out over March 1st -April 30th during the NCEP daily winds from 1950-2019. The galleons were given 3 days to sail south and then head directly east, while given the ability to adjust their course more directly towards Embocadero de San Bernardino after around 25 days. Any land encountered before nearing the Philippines was ignored. Historically the voyages were usually completed in less than 120 days (Garcia et al. 2001: 2444) although longer voyages occurred, and a maximum of 125 days was given to the simulated voyages. The parameters were chosen to give the simulated galleons every chance of successful landfall, not least by leaving during the main months chosen by the original sailors, rather than focus on overall survivability of year-round voyaging.

The simulations produced some interesting results relating to the seafaring itself (Figure 7). Initially, sailing out of Acapulco could be quite difficult in some years, with the winds often making it time-consuming to make good progress to the south. While the original galleons would probably have waited to start on a voyage when the winds were favorable, this did point to the fact that in some years the window for the crossing was often challenging, and a bad start could have repercussions later in the voyage including limited food and fresh water supplies.

Figure 9 shows the length of simulated voyages for 1950-2019 compared with the month of departure. It illustrates the most dominant trend that leaving in March rather than April meant voyages averaged over 7 days shorter and were much easier.

Figure 7: Simulated voyages across the northern Pacific showing the shortest voyage (dashed line, March 1996), average voyage (solid line, March 1967) and slowest (dotted line, April 2003)

Figure 8: Length of voyages leaving in March and April of each year, 1950-2019, from Acapulco to the Philippines showing overall trend of voyage length

Whether the results are impacted by ENSO is more elusive to demonstrate. Figure 9 summarizes the annual voyage lengths color-coded using a measure of the Southern Oscillation Index (NOAA 2024). The Southern Oscillation Index (SOI) provides a measure of air temperature differences

between the eastern and western tropical zones in the Pacific. Long periods of negative SOI values are typical of El Niño episodes with unusually warm ocean waters across the eastern tropical Pacific. La Niña episodes coincide with abnormally cold ocean waters across the eastern tropical Pacific and positive SOI values (NOAA 2024). Monthly values from 1951 were available to download (NOAA 2024), and averaged for February through to July for each year to provide a general indication of prevailing conditions covering the simulated voyages.

A general trend of longer voyages in more recent conditions is visible in both Figure 8 and Figure 9. In the 1950s most of the simulated crossings took less than 70 days (mean 66 ± 6) quickly rising in the later decades where, by the 2010s, crossings averaged 77 ± 9 days, with the increase slightly longer for late-season (April) departures. There is also a great deal of fluctuation year-on-year which starts in the mid-1960s. There was little clear correlation directly between voyage length and SOI. Stronger trade winds characteristic of La Niña events were expected to speed up the voyages, but in the simulated voyages, they were marginally slower on average. Examination of the average speeds of voyages suggested that La Niña conditions provided faster journeys to around the 190° longitude but then were slower than both neutral and El Niño conditions for the rest of the journey. Such observations are based on the annual averaged SOI values and in reality, would have been much more complex than summarised here. Historically for the Manila Galleons sailing from Acapulco, this was much less of an issue with the cycle much less common.

5. Discussion

Seafaring is central to many narratives of human history; however, our ability to investigate ancient seafaring archaeologically is constrained by the preservation of maritime technology and the practical limitations of investigating seafaring events over deep ocean spaces. These uncertainties leave open a wide range of historical possibilities, but also present opportunities to explore them by way of computational modeling. In this paper, we update progress on the agent-based simulation tool Virtual Vaka (Davies and Bickler 2015), introducing new capabilities for navigation, vessel performance, environmental data and modelling.

Agent-Based models, such as Virtual Vaka, continue to provide useful insights into ancient seafaring across the globe. The current version provides a globally oriented flexible and scalable solution to explore a range of archaeological problems. Simulating seafaring combines information from a range of sources to explore the process of exploration and travel. This complements the research on the technology required to undertake voyages (e.g., Damon 2017: 296ff; Irwin et al. 2019) and historical and ethnographic descriptions of the canoes recorded during Contact between European explorers and subsequent indigenous recording of technology (e.g., Anderson 2022, 2024b; Farr et al. 2025, Slayton 2018, Slayton et al. 2025). Drawing on documented archaeological cases, we demonstrate a number of these new mechanisms to examine some of the major arguments relating to settlement and interaction in the Pacific and highlight the use of voyaging as a lens on past and present climate change.

Figure 9: Boxplot showing distribution of the length of voyages leaving in March and April of each year from Acapulco to the Philippines. Shaded by averaged Southern Oscillation Index (No SOI data for 1950)

Challenges remain with the use of modern environmental data typically a proxy for past weather conditions (see e.g., Irwin 1992, Montenegro et al. 2006, 2008, 2014, 2016 and other simulations discussed in the paper). This is especially problematic in the Pleistocene but still an issue even in more recent historical periods. Dousset and Di Piazza's (2021) simulation suggesting good sailing conditions for trips to Lizard Island in Australia from Near Oceania (including the Solomon Islands and the islands around the Papua New Guinea) use their 1998 wind data as their exemplar. However, as we have shown in some of the simulations here (Figure 9), the 1998 winds were unusual during a strong ENSO cycle in this part of the Pacific. This illustrates how shifting conditions could open up and enhance pathways in some conditions and shutdown or limit others in a very short space of time. Given recently reported pottery finds in Lizard Island (Ulm et al. 2024), our understanding of the relationships between indigenous Australians and Austronesian sailors may only be in its infancy.

Even for later time periods, the match between modern data and past conditions is a source of contention. Goodwin et al. (2014) use bi-decadal climate modelling, rather than modern data, of the South Pacific during the 800-1300 AD period to show how migrations routes to and from East Polynesia might have been influenced. They argue that initial colonization routes to the Polynesian extremes, Aotearoa/New Zealand, and Rapa Nui/Easter Island, may have occurred during periods where downward routes were easier and good windward capacity was not essential (Goodwin et al. 2014), especially during the period around 1140-1260 AD.

However, sailors do not sail through climate, but weather, and while voyaging pathways may have changed during major climate shifts, different strategies for travel between places might have occurred during those periods. Seasonal shifts may have allowed for voyages to have occurred at different times of the year, evolving constantly throughout the movement of people across the Pacific. Simulations of previous weather patterns and voyaging may show that voyages could be made with limited windward capability if other technologies were being developed, such as improving positional awareness, that increased the likelihood of finding and surviving.

The primary reason we simulate seafaring is to build connections across the yawning gap that exists between importance placed on seafaring in human history and the fragmentary data that exists to inform on it (Slayton et al. 2025). Humans have been moving across the water for thousands if not millions of years (e.g., Hölzchen, et al. 2022, Smith 2020). Our unique distribution as a species has depended on, and many of the critical environmental and social changes that have occurred throughout time began when people set out in boats headed toward the horizon. Oral and written records, and a few lasting physical traces, provide the foundation of our knowledge; most hope for improving our understanding comes from techniques like experimentation and modeling that let us explore that uncertainty in systematic ways (see also Farr et al. 2025, McDonald 2022).

So why are we going to the trouble of building user interfaces, visual outputs, and customization functionality in Virtual Vaka? A principal reason is that ours is not the only expertise that matters. Models of any sort create a theoretical space in which we can explore potential outcomes of historical processes, but given enough common structure, this space can also be negotiated among many different knowledge holders. In this way, they can act as boundary objects (sensu Star and Griesemer 1989), used collaboratively to build shared understanding across multiple ways of knowing. To better serve this purpose, models must be flexible enough to be used in different domains and contexts, and clear enough to enable discussion and comparison across them (Perttola 2022: 716).

The models built in the late 20th century were constrained in large part by technology; indeed, Levinson et al. (1973) were physically involved in the computing of the 1970s, regularly switching out the tapes that held their modeled wind and geography. These limitations meant that most simulations were built for very specific purposes, used solely by their developers, and often lost to obsolescence. In 2024, many of these constraints no longer exist; therefore, building simulations that enable engagement, collaboration, and reuse is not just possible, but should be a priority. We hope to use Virtual Vaka as a tool not just for generating hypotheses and testing ideas, but to facilitate conversations (Slayton 2018).

There is no single solution for modeling past seafaring (see Fitzpatrick 2025; Slayton et al. 2025 for further discussion). Different tools are needed to address different aspects, and so many projects are engaging with this diversity and making methods available to others (see Slayton 2018 for an overview). Here, we have demonstrated a tool that can be used to explore seafaring questions from around the globe with an emphasis on individual-level actions in response to specific conditions encountered at sea and seafarers' different motivations for travel. The results show that while their primary goal may be related to explicating the past, the simulation provides a method of investigating local, regional, and global climatological changes (e.g., McDonald 2022). Incorporating the older knowledge around ancient seafaring provides an experiential insight into our current and future world.

Data and Code Availability

Simulation code available on [Github](#). Primary data available at provider websites identified in the references. Contact authors for any additional information.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, software and analysis and by Simon Bickler and Benjamin Davies; writing—original draft preparation, Simon Bickler; writing—review and editing, Benjamin Davies. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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References

- Anderson, A. 2017. "Changing perspectives upon Māori colonisation voyaging." *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand* 47(3): 222–231.
- Anderson, A. 2022. "An historical analysis of waka unua and the Māori sail." *Journal of the Polynesian Society* 131(1): 33–70.
- Anderson, A. 2024a. "Looking for lost proficiency in East Polynesian voyaging traditions and ethnology." *The Journal of Pacific History* 59(3): 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223344.2024.2321393>
- Anderson, A. 2024b. "The origins of prehistoric sailing technologies in the Pacific Ocean." In *The Oxford Handbook of Island and Coastal Archaeology*, edited by S. M. Fitzpatrick and J. Erlandson. Oxford: Oxford Academic, online edition, August 16, 2023.
- Avis, C., Á. Montenegro, and A. Weaver. 2007. "The Discovery of Western Oceania: A New Perspective." *Journal of Island & Coastal Archaeology* 2:197–209. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564890701518557>
- Bevan, A. 2015. "The data deluge." *Antiquity* 89(348): 1473–1484.
- Bonjean, F., and G. S. E. Lagerloef. 2002. "Diagnostic model and analysis of the surface currents in the tropical Pacific Ocean." *American Meteorological Society* 32: 2938–2954.
- Callaghan, R. T. 2003a. "The use of simulation models to estimate frequency and location of Japanese Edo Period wrecks along the Canadian Pacific Coast." *Canadian Journal of Archaeology* 27(1): 74–94.
- Callaghan, R. T. 2003b. "Prehistoric trade between Ecuador and West Mexico: A computer simulation of coastal voyages." *Antiquity* 77(298): 796–804.
- Callaghan, R. T. 2015. "Drift voyages across the mid-Atlantic." *Antiquity* 89(345): 724–731.
- Callaghan, R. T., and S. M. Fitzpatrick. 2008. "Examining prehistoric migration patterns in the Palauan Archipelago: A computer simulated analysis of drift voyaging." *Asian Perspectives* 47(1): 28–44.
- Chang, W., J. Cheng, J. Allaire, C. Sievert, B. Schloerke, Y. Xie, J. Allen, J. McPherson, A. Dipert, and B. Borges. 2023. *Shiny: Web Application Framework for R*. R package version 1.8.0. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=shiny>
- Damon, F. 2017. *Trees, Knots and Outriggers: Environmental Knowledge in the Northeast Kula Ring*. New York: Berghahn Books.
- Davies, B. 2018. "Weaving the Common Threads of Formation and Simulation." In *Exploring Oceans of Data: Papers from the 44th Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in*

Archaeology, Oslo, 29 March – April 2, 2016, edited by M. Matsumoto and E. Uleberg, 481–494. Oslo: University of Oslo.

Davies, B., and S. H. Bickler. 2015. "Sailing the Simulated Seas: A New Simulation for Evaluating Prehistoric Seafaring." In *Across Space and Time: Papers from the 41st Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology*, Perth, 25–28 March 2013, edited by A. Traviglia, 215–223. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press.

Di Piazza, A., P. Di Piazza, and E. Pearthree. 2007. "Sailing virtual canoes across Oceania: Revisiting island accessibility." *Journal of Archaeological Science* 34: 1219–1225.

Dousset, L., and A. Di Piazza. 2021. "Mapping prehistoric sailing routes to Lizard Island and beyond." *Journal of Pacific Archaeology* 12(1): 16–31.

Evans, B. M. 2008. "Simulating Polynesian double-hulled canoe voyaging: combining digital and experimental data to prepare for a voyage to Rapa Nui (Easter Island)." In *Canoes of the Grand Ocean*. BAR International Series 1802, edited by A. Di Piazza and E. Pearthree, 143–154. Oxford: Archaeopress.

Farr, H., B. Bérard, J. Genz, J. Leidwanger, and E. Slayton. 2025. "Navigating the Narrative: Integrating Traditional Knowledge and Embodied Practice within Computational Models of Ancient Seafaring." *Journal of Maritime Archaeology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-025-09470-6>

Finney, B. 1997. *Voyage of Rediscovery: A Cultural Odyssey through Polynesia*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Fitzpatrick, S. M. 2013. "Seafaring capabilities in the pre-Columbian Caribbean." *Journal of Maritime Archaeology* 8(1): 101–138.

Fitzpatrick, S. M. 2025. "Leviathan's Revenge: Seafaring Simulations, Deep History and the Rise of Computational Modelling". *Journal of Maritime Archaeology* 20:655–665. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-025-09465-3>

Fitzpatrick, S. M., and R. T. Callaghan. 2013. "Estimating trajectories of colonisation to the Mariana Islands, Western Pacific." *Antiquity* 87(337): 840–853.

Gal, D., H. Saaroni, and D. Cvikel. 2021. "A new method for examining maritime mobility of direct crossings with contrary prevailing winds in the Mediterranean during antiquity." *Journal of Archaeological Science* 129: 105369.

Garcia, R. R., H. F. Diaz, R. G. Herrera, J. Eischied, M. del Rosario Prieto, E. Hernandez, L. Gimeno, F. R. Duran, and A. M. Bascary. 2001. "Atmospheric circulation changes in the tropical Pacific inferred from the voyages of the Manila galleons in the sixteenth-eighteenth centuries." *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 82(11): 2435–2455.

- Goodwin, I. D., S. A. Browning, and A. J. Anderson. 2014. "Climate windows for Polynesian voyaging." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, September 2014, 201408918. [URL]
- Gunn, M. 1980. "Etak and the ghost islands of the Carolines." *Journal of the Polynesian Society* 89(4): 499–507.
- Heyerdahl, T. 1968. *Sea Routes to Polynesia*. London: Allen & Unwin.
- Horvath, S. M., and B. R. Finney. 1976. "Paddling experiments and the question of Polynesian voyaging." In *Pacific Navigation and Voyaging*, edited by B. Finney, 47–54. Wellington: Polynesian Society.
- Hölzchen, E. H., C. Willmes, I. P. Anwar, A. Mateos, J. Rodríguez, J. O. Berndt, and I. J. Timm. 2022. "Estimating Crossing Success of Human Agents Across Sea Straits Out of Africa in the Late Pleistocene." *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 590:110845. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2022.110845>.
- Irwin, G. 1992. *The Prehistoric Exploration and Colonisation of the Pacific*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Irwin, G., S. Bickler, and P. Quirke. 1990. "Voyaging by canoe and computer: Experiments in the settlement of the Pacific Ocean." *Antiquity* 64(242): 34–50.
- Irwin, G., R. G. J. Flay, L. Dudley, and D. Johns. 2022. "The sailing performance of ancient Polynesian canoes and the early settlement of East Polynesia." *Archaeology in Oceania* 57: 1–17.
- Irwin, G., B. Shaw, and A. McAlister. 2019. "The origins of the Kula Ring: Archaeological and maritime perspectives from the Southern Massim and Mailu areas of Papua New Guinea." *Archaeology in Oceania* 54: 1–16.
- Kalnay, E., M. Kanamitsu, R. Kistler, W. Collins, et al. 1996. "The NCEP/NCAR 40-year reanalysis project." *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 77: 437–470.
- Kimball, J. 2009. *Physics of sailing*. Boca Raton: CRC Press.
- Levinson, M., R. G. Ward, and J. W. Webb. 1973. *The Settlement of Polynesia: A Computer Simulation*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- McDonald, R. A. 2022. *He moana pukepuke e ekengia e te waka: Navigating a Changing Climate: A Waka Voyaging Perspective*. PhD diss., University of Waikato.
- Montenegro, Á. 2024. "Seafaring in Prehistory: Simulations and Experiments". In S. M. Fitzpatrick & J. M. Erlandson (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Island and Coastal Archaeology* (1st ed.). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197607770.013.17>

- Montenegro, Á., C. Avis, and A. Weaver. 2008. "Modeling the prehistoric arrival of the sweet potato in Polynesia." *Journal of Archaeological Science* 35: 355–367.
- Montenegro, Á., R. T. Callaghan, and S. M. Fitzpatrick. 2014. "From west to east: Environmental influences on the rate and pathways of Polynesian colonization." *The Holocene* 24(2): 242–256.
- Montenegro, Á., R. T. Callaghan, and S. M. Fitzpatrick. 2016. "Using seafaring simulations and shortest-hop trajectories to model the prehistoric colonization of Remote Oceania." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113(45): 12685–12690.
- Montenegro, A., R. Heatherington, M. Eby, and A. Weaver. 2006. "Modelling pre-historic transoceanic crossings into the Americas." *Quaternary Science Reviews* 25: 1323–1338.
- NCEP Daily Global Analyses data. n.d. Provided by the NOAA/OAR/ESRL PSL, Boulder, Colorado, USA. <https://psl.noaa.gov/data/gridded/data.ncep.reanalysis.html>
- NOAA Climate Prediction Center. 2024. *Southern Oscillation Index (SOI) data*. https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/analysis_monitoring/ensocycle/soi.shtml
- OSCAR Project Office. n.d. *Ocean Surface Current Analyses – Real Time*. <http://www.oscar.noaa.gov>. Accessed June 2020.
- Palmer, C. 2009. "Windward sailing capabilities of ancient vessels." *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 38(2): 314–330.
- Perttola, W. 2022. "Digital navigator on the seas of the Selden Map of China: Sequential least-cost path analysis using dynamic wind data." *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory* 29: 688–721.
- R Core Team. 2023. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing.
- Rorabaugh, A. N. 2025. "Seascapes of the Unreal: Using Agent-Based Modeling to Examine Traditional Coast Salish Maritime Mobility." In *The Archaeology of Seafaring in Small-Scale Societies: Negotiating Watery Worlds*, edited by A. García-Piquer, M. Fauvelle, and C. Grier, 43–57. Gainesville: University Press of Florida.
- Slayton, E. R. 2018. *Seascape Corridors: Modeling Routes to Connect Communities Across the Caribbean Sea*. Leiden: Sidestone Press.
- Slayton, E., K. Jarriel, A. Montenegro, C. Safadi, K. Smith, and S. Zaia. 2025. "Seafaring and Modelling." *Journal of Maritime Archaeology* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11457-025-09455-5>.
- Smith, K. 2020. *Modelling Seafaring in Iron Age Atlantic Europe*. University of Oxford.
- Star, S. L., and J. R. Griesemer. 1989. "Institutional ecology, 'translations' and boundary objects: Amateurs and professionals in Berkeley's Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907–39." *Social Studies of Science* 19(3): 387–420.

Ulm, S., I. J. McNiven, G. R. Summerhayes, P-H. Wu, M. M. E. Bunbury, F. Petchey, Q. Hua, R. Skelly, A. B. J. Lambrides, C. Rowe, K. M. Lowe, C. H. Reepmeyer, C. Maclaurin, K. G. P. Woo, M. Harris, S. B. Morgan, K. L. Turner-Kose, S. A. Slater, J. D. Connelly, M. C. Kneppers, K. Szabó, A. Fairbairn, S. G. Haberle, F. Hopf, R. Bultitude, J. Ash, S. E. Lewis, R. J. Beaman, J. X. Leon, M. C. McDowell, M. Potter, B. Connelly, C. Little, S. Jackson, J. McCarthy, L. D. Nothdurft, J-X. Zhao, M. I. Bird, M. W. Felgate, and B. Cobus. 2024. "Early Aboriginal pottery production and offshore island occupation on Jiigurrū (Lizard Island Group), Great Barrier Reef, Australia." *Quaternary Science Reviews* 333: 108624.

United States Coast Guard. 2013. U.S. Coast Guard Addendum to the United States National Search and Rescue Supplement (NSS) to the International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual (IAMSAR). COMDTINST M16130.2F.

Verhagen, P. 2018. "Spatial analysis in archaeology: Moving into new territories." In *Digital geoarchaeology: New techniques for interdisciplinary human-environmental research*, edited by C. Siart, M. Forbriger, and O. Bubenzer, 11–25. Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Wild, S. 1985. "Voyaging to Australia: 30,000 years ago." *Computer & Graphics* 10(3): 207–212.